

INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
ON FERMENTED
FOODS

27-30TH
OF OCTOBER
2025

BOOK OF
ABSTRACTS

● The 1st International Conference on Fermented Foods 2025 (ICFF 2025) is a unique worldwide opportunity that brings together leading experts, researchers, and industry professionals from all continents and many countries to delve into the latest advancements and innovations and future exploitation of the potential. Fermented foods, cornerstones of human nutrition for millennia, have witnessed a great resurgence of interest due to their profound impact on human health, food security and safety, nutrition, industrial business, and sustainability. Because of this importance, fermented foods still face evolving challenges, such as how to advance tradition into future foods with different perspectives; how to steer the processes and guide the microbiomes; how to develop innovative biotechnologies to impact human health, the global food safety, and security and precision; and how to exploit the potential for dignifying food waste and reducing food loss and create the next generation of sustainable foods, also responding to the need of using non-conventional protein sources. Sharing knowledge and best practices globally is vital for accelerating this transformative transition.

This dedicated conference on fermented foods is essential to address these challenges and capitalise on the growing opportunities. By bringing together researchers, industry professionals, and policymakers, we can foster collaboration, advance scientific knowledge, and drive innovation in the production and consumption of fermented foods. We are committed to fostering a vibrant exchange of ideas and knowledge sharing among attendees from diverse backgrounds. Through keynote presentations, oral and poster sessions, and interactive workshops, we aim to create a stimulating environment for sharing knowledge, establishing synergistic collaboration, and supporting networking.

ICFF will become a recurring event held every three years, with its permanent locations at NOI Techpark, aiming to be the unique reference for researchers and professionals in this sector. Because of the great relevance of fermented foods in human tradition, society, well-being and economy, ICFF will be the recurrent meeting where scientific achievements will be presented and discussed, and results transferred to industry.

Marco Gobetti
Chief Scientist, NOI Techpark

● Dear participants,

Fermentation is one of humanity's oldest biotechnologies. For millennia, it has enabled us to preserve food, nourish communities, and create flavours that define cultures. Across the world – and especially here in South Tyrol – traditional dishes are rich with fermented ingredients, from cheeses and breads to cured meats and fermented vegetables. These foods are not only a testament to our heritage, but also to the ingenuity of generations who harnessed natural processes to ensure sustenance and safety.

Today, fermentation stands at the threshold of new opportunities. Thanks to advances in biotechnology, we can now understand and control fermentation processes with unprecedented precision. This opens the door to foods that are healthier, tastier, longer lasting, and more sustainable. By valorising by-products and optimising microbial activity, we are able to create products that meet the demands of modern consumers while respecting the environment.

Bozen/Bolzano has become renowned for its expertise in food fermentation. Our region's research centres and companies are at the forefront of innovation, blending tradition with cutting-edge science. It is therefore a great honour for us to host the very first ICFF Conference here in Bozen / Bolzano. With this new initiative, we are bringing together the world's leading experts in the field of fermented foods to share knowledge, spark new ideas, and build lasting collaborations in our region.

What awaits you at ICFF? Inspiring lectures from leading scientists and practitioners, engaging discussions on the future of fermented foods, and the chance to discover new approaches and solutions. The conference is not only a forum for exchanging expertise, but also a unique opportunity for networking – whether during the sessions, in informal conversations, or on our joint excursion, where you can experience South Tyrol's landscapes.

We hope you enjoy your time in South Tyrol, find inspiration in the diversity of perspectives, and leave with new connections and ideas that will shape the future of fermented foods.

With best wishes for a successful and memorable conference,

Philipp
Achammer
Provincial Minister
responsible for NOI

Helga
Thaler Ausserhofer
NOI President

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- **Nicholas Bokulich**

Dept. of Health Sciences and Technology ETH Zürich [Switzerland]

- **Christophe Courtin**

Laboratory of Food Chemistry and Biochemistry at KU Leuven [Belgium]

- **Luc De Vuyst**

[Belgium]

- **Raffaella Di Cagno**

Faculty of Agricultural, Environmental and Food Sciences,
Free University of Bozen-Bolzano [Italy]

- **Monica Gatti**

Department of Food and Pharmaceutical Sciences,
University of Parma [Italy]

- **Marco Gobetti**

Faculty of Agricultural, Environmental and Food Sciences, Free University
of Bozen-Bolzano [Italy] Chief Scientist NOI Techpark, Bolzano [Italy]

- **Nam Soo Han**

Chungbuk National University [South Korea]

- **Alan Kelly**

University College Cork (UCC) [Ireland]

- **Rosalba Lanciotti**

Department of Agricultural and Food Sciences, Alma Mater Studiorum,
University of Bologna [Italy]

- **Alfonso D.R. Lazaro**

Research Centre for Emerging Pathogens and Public Health at the
University of Burgos [Spain]

- **Shao Quan Liu**

Department of Food Science and Technology, National University of
Singapore [Singapore]

- **Maria Marco**

Department of Food Science and Technology The University of California,
Davis CA [USA]

- **Eddy J. Smid**

Laboratory of Food Microbiology, Wageningen University [The Netherland]

- **Effie Tsakalidou**

Department of Food Science and Human Nutrition, Agricultural University
of Athens [Athens]

- **Douwe Van Sinderen**

School of Microbiology University College Cork [Ireland]

- **Emanuele Zannini**

Department of Environmental Biology, Sapienza University of Rome [Italy]

- **Jian Zhao**

School of Chemical Engineering, the University of New South Wales,
Sydney [Australia]

-
- Kashika Arora

ICOFF

- Raffaella Di Cagno

Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Micro4Food, ICOFF

- Matthias Fill

NOI Techpark

- Sandra Fleischmann

NOI Techpark

- Lisa Geier

NOI Techpark

- Olga Nikoloudaki

Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Micro4Food, ICOFF

- Andrea Polo

Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Micro4Food, ICOFF

- Federica Pompeo

NOI Techpark

- Ali Tlais Zein Alabiden

Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Micro4Food, ICOFF

Fermentation of oil pumpkin and butternut squash pulps: impact on chemical composition and rheological properties

[1] **Biljana Cvetković**
[1] Miona Belović
[2] Ilinka Pećinar
[1] Aleksandra Bajić
[1] Ana Varga
[1] Marijana Đorđević
[1] Miljana Đorđević

● This study explores the impact of lactic fermentation on the chemical composition, rheological properties, and nutritional profile of oil pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo* var. *Styriaca*) and butternut squash (*Cucurbita Moschata*) pulps. Fermented and non-fermented samples were analyzed for β -carotene content, particle size distribution, viscosity, and colorimetric properties. Raw pumpkin puree samples from *Moscata* had the highest L (lightness) value at 49.57 ± 0.67 , while raw *Stryaca* puree had a lower L value (41.16 ± 1.42). The particle size analysis of both *Moscata* and *Stryaca* pumpkin purees revealed that the mean particle size for fermented *Moscata* puree was $120.9 \mu\text{m}$ (± 16.2), while for fermented *Stryaca* puree it was $124.6 \mu\text{m}$ (± 17.6), which were significantly smaller compared to raw and blanched samples, with mean sizes of $174.9 \mu\text{m}$ (± 34.6) and $168.3 \mu\text{m}$ (± 21.1) for raw *Moscata* and *Stryaca*, respectively. The rheological measurements revealed that raw *Moscata* puree had the highest apparent viscosity ($0.46 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$) and consistency index ($15.54 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{sn}$), while fermented *Stryaca* puree had the lowest viscosity ($0.06 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$) and consistency ($0.73 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{sn}$). The hysteresis loop area was largest in raw *Moscata* puree ($36,040 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$). Raman spectroscopy and principal component analysis (PCA) revealed significant biochemical changes, particularly in carotenoid and phenolic compound profiles, distinguishing fermented from non-fermented pulps. The results demonstrate that fermentation modifies both the structural and functional properties of pumpkin pulps, with implications for their use in food applications.

[1] Institute of Food Technology,
University of Novi Sad, Bulevar cara
Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

[2] Department of Agrobotany,
Faculty of Agriculture, University
of Belgrade, Nemanjina 6, Zemun,
11080 Belgrade, Serbia

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